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Communication: From Illusion to Communion

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Abstract: Based on the insight from Pope Francis’s encyclical letter, “Fertilla Tutti” “we are looking into the illusion of communication. For this, we go through communication, traditional communication, and modern communication, in order to see how people are switching from traditional media to new media. Digital communication wants to bring everything out into the open; people’s lives are combed over, laid bare and bandied about, often anonymously. The more we communicate, the less we suffer, and the better we feel about everything around us

Keywords: media, communication, traditional, modern, illusion.

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Introduction

The concept, “communication” is central to all forms of human interactions cum endeavours. It is a two-way interactive process, between the sender and receiver that involves the sharing of ideas and experiences. According to Oso, communication is an important resource for any social organization. This is true given that communication, irrespective of the level or setting, carries with it meaningful messages that could lead to a healthy exchange of ideas, knowledge, feeds, experience, and other factual information. Communication relates to the exchange of facts, opinions, or emotions by two or more people, and in an organization, it could be words, letters, symbols, or messages, in a way that one organization member shares meaning and understanding with another. Many scientists agree that communication is the transfer of information from one person to another, but only if the information is understandable by the receiver. Communication maintains and animates life. It is also the motor and expression of social activity and civilization. It leads people and peoples from instinct to inspiration, through an unregulated process and system of enquiry, command and control. Communication creates a common pool of ideas, strengthens the feeling of togetherness through the exchange of messages, and translates thoughts into action. It integrates knowledge, organization, and power and runs as a thread linking the

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earliest memory of man to his noblest aspiration through constant striving for a better life.

Media has changed the way humans interact with each other and it has also evolved tremendously over the years. Many people are switching from traditional media to new media and every day we spend much qualities of our time on technology. Whether it is to communicate through mobile phones or delivering of work through e-mails or enjoying entertainment such as watching television and so on, our life just seems to revolve around technology.

In order to arrive at this, first I want to reflect on communication, and then on traditional communication. It leads to modern communication, and finally, the illusion of communication. This leads me to study the significance of this topic and apply it to my own life.

Communication and Communion

The exchange of information or passing of information, ideas or thought from one person to the other or from one end to the other is communication. According to some scholars, communication is "a process of meaningful interaction among human beings. More specifically, it is the process by which meanings are perceived and understandings are reached among human beings." Communication may be understood as "an exchange of facts, ideas, opinions or emotions by two or more persons." Thus communication brings people together, closer to each other, leading to genuine communion.

Communication is one of the important tools that aid us in connecting with people. Whether you are a student or a working professional, good communication is something that will get you far ahead. Proper communication can help you to solve a number of issues and resolve problems. Communication is not merely essential but the need of the hour. It allows you to get the trust of the people and, at the same time, carry better opportunities before you. Some important points to be considered are as follows:

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- Help to Build Relationships

No matter what you are studying or working on, communication can aid you in building a relationship with people. If you are studying, you communicate with classmates and teachers to build a relationship with them. Likewise, in offices and organizations too, you make relationships with the staff, the boss, and other people around.

- Improve the Working Environment

There are a number of issues which can be handled through the right and effective communication. Even planning needs communication, both written and verbal. Hence, it is essential to be good at them so as to fill in the communication gap.

- Foster Strong Team

Communication helps to build a strong team environment in the office and other places. Any work which requires teamwork is done in a team. It is only possible if the head communicates everything well and in the right direction.

- Find the Right Solutions

Through communication, anyone can find solutions to even serious problems. When we talk, we get ideas from people that help us solve issues. This is where communication comes into play. Powerful communication is the strength of any organization and can help it in many ways.

- Earns More Respect

If our communication skills are admirable, people will love and give us respect. If there is any problems, we will be the first person to be contacted. Thus, it will increase our importance. Hence, we can say that communications skills can make a big change to your reputation in society.

Traditional Communication

Traditional communication means that two or more people are carrying on a conversation in person, so they can see body language and other non-verbal signals. Much of this is lost in non-traditional communication, making it trickier to convey ideas. Even as tech continues to improve, many people still prefer interpersonal interaction. Human interaction is

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powerful. Making time to interact with potential clients face-to-face leaves a lasting impression. Our effort to build relationships can yield high returns for your organization. This traditional communication can bring new business opportunities.

In this time and age, people can communicate in many different ways rather than speaking face to face. Technology is worldwide and you can communicate with people from anywhere in the world in a matter of minutes. Communications technology can include mobile phones, tablets, iPods, iPhones, iPads, and social media.

Modern Communication

In today's world, communication has become very easy for people to contact and communicate with people around the world, and it is because of communication technology. Mobile phones are the best example of communication technology. Through mobile phones, people can contact and communicate with people, friends, and relatives around the world very easily and at less cost. Before the invention of mobile phones and telephones, people used letters for communication with their relatives and friends. It was very difficult for people to communicate through letters because sending letters takes a lot of time and also charges money.

Technology wastes our precious time. We might wonder how I can say that modern technology wastes our precious time. Actually, this is one of the bad effects of technology on us. But we didn't recognize it. There are a lot of modern technological gadgets that most people use and waste their precious time. Like television, video games, play stations, music players, and most mobile phones. People mostly use

these kinds of technological devices most of the time and waste their precious time doing unimportant activities. They use these devices during their work time, study time, and even in bed instead of sleeping. They like to use such kinds of modern technological devices.

The Illusion of Communication

One of the disadvantages of using social media is the loss of social skills. The reason behind this is that many people are found to be socially awkward when it comes to interacting with people in person. Therefore, they are unable to converse well with others. Oddly enough, while closed and intolerant attitudes towards others are on the rise, distances are otherwise shrinking or disappearing to the point that the right to privacy scarcely exists. Everything has become a kind of spectacle to be examined and inspected, and people's lives are now under constant surveillance. Digital communication wants to bring everything out into the open; people's lives are combed over, laid bare and bandied about, often anonymously. Respect for others disintegrates, and even as we dismiss, ignore or keep others distant, we can shamelessly peer into every detail of their lives.

For their part, digital campaigns of hatred and destruction are not – as some would have us believe – a positive form of mutual support, but simply an association of individuals united against a perceived common enemy. “Digital media can also expose people to the risk of addiction, isolation and a

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gradual loss of contact with concrete reality, blocking the development of authentic interpersonal relationships”. [46] They lack the physical gestures, facial expressions, moments of silence, body language and even the smells, the trembling of hands, the blushes and perspiration that speak to us and are a part of human communication. Digital relationships, which do not demand the slow and gradual cultivation of friendships, stable interaction or the building of a consensus that matures over time, have the appearance of sociability. Yet they do not really build community; instead, they tend to disguise and expand the very individualism that finds expression in xenophobia and in contempt for the vulnerable. Digital connectivity is not enough to build bridges. It is not capable of uniting humanity.

- Distraction from Real Life

Sitting next to someone who is engaged in a heated text message conversation can cause you to feel lonely and left out. When people use technology as their primary means of communication, they can become so engrossed in their gadgets that they acquire a form of tunnel vision. Without realizing it, these thumb talkers may forget about job responsibilities, neglect relationships with family and friends and become dangerous drivers.

- The Lost Art of Conversation

Technology such as text messages and email allows us to communicate in short, carefully-edited sentences that lack immediacy and completely remove the contextual information provided by tone of voice and body language. As a result, people who connect with others primarily through technology might find it difficult to engage in

normal conversation, since they may have issues understanding non-verbal cues due to lack of practice with face-to-face interaction that can't be paused, edited or filtered.

- Deteriorating Language

Books, dictionaries and treatises have been written on the vocabulary and peculiarities of online and text messaging slang. This slang can prove extremely confusing for people who are not native English speakers, making it harder to discern the meaning of a sentence. People who regularly text or chat online may end up using it, out of sheer habit, even in situations where it is inappropriate or out of place, such as in business messages or school essays.

- Enabling Rudeness

Because communicating through technology creates a barrier between people that isn't there when speaking face to face, some may find it easier to be rude and aggressive. Insulting or threatening messages from anonymous commenters are par for the course for anybody who regularly publishes online content, and even lack of anonymity doesn't alleviate the issue. So Facebook arguments and the like are also relatively common. Sherry Turkle, professor of the social studies of science and technology at MIT, suggests that this happens because technology keeps us from having to see the reaction of the person on the receiving end of the message, making it harder to empathize with him.

Conclusion

Communication is of the utmost importance. It is important to share one's thoughts and feelings in order to live a fuller and happier life. The more we communicate, the less we suffer, and the better we feel about everything around us. However, it is all the more necessary to learn the art of effective communication to put across one's point well gently and genuinely. So we need both

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traditional and modern communication. When we take this together, it's so helpful to our development. We just remember that both have advantages and disadvantages. So we want to select the good side and remove the negative effects. Genuine communication makes us good and understanding people. Such communication will help us to encounter the other with empathy! That is true communion.

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